

USE OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF LOGICAL THINKING IN ELEMENTARY GRADES

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Annotation: This article discusses the method of developing logical thinking in elementary grades. To develop the worldview and logical thinking of primary school students, it was thought about working with different types of assignments.

Keywords: logical thinking, logic, logicity, logical task, primary education.

Introduction. After the independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan, especially at the threshold of the 21st century, the attention to socio-economic and spiritual-educational spheres increased. Many fields are developing and flourishing. It should be noted that it is not a secret to anyone that more attention is being paid to the field of education. In the conditions of Uzbekistan, where reforms are being carried out in the socio-economic, material and spiritual spheres, the need for broad-minded, rational thinking youth is the demand of the times. Because only people with broad thinking and worldview are able to ensure the development of society.

Development of logical thinking of elementary school students is an important issue. Because the conscious activity of students at the junior school age makes them thirsty for knowledge. At this age, students have the opportunity to improve knowledge, manners, stability of memory, stability of attention, which they should get from outside. It is at this age that the primary teacher's main task is to develop logical thinking in students. At this age, it is necessary to guide primary school students in the right way and to make them interested in science, technology and other professions. It is important to form a sense of patriotism in the hearts of elementary school students in order to encourage their thoughts, to increase their interest in professions, and to nurture them with deep eyes on the future.

Literature review. The development of logical thinking is related to thinking as a way of perceiving existence, reality, and is formed in the process of working with arithmetic operations, working on logical problems, conscious use of digital technologies in the educational process, and organizing independent work.

In many cases, the requirements imposed on students by the teacher do not serve to develop logical thinking. Focusing only on the acquisition of knowledge in education leads to a decrease in the quality and effectiveness of education. However, only students with broad logical thinking can master knowledge independently. Therefore, it is very important to develop logical thinking in primary grades.

The word "logic" is derived from the Arabic language and is the Arabic expression of the word "logic" which means "thought", "word", "law" derived from the Greek language. (encyclopedic dictionary of philosophy)

"Logic" means logic, rationale, legality, fundamentality.

It is no secret that mathematics is the basis for the development of logical thinking of elementary school students. Solving mathematical examples-problems makes thinking easier for elementary school students. It is very important to develop logical thinking in elementary school students. Because, at the junior school age, students get the foundation of knowledge they need. It is this knowledge that will make it easier for subjects to be studied in the future and will serve as a program.

Doctor of science of TDPU named after Nizomi, professor -Ibragimov Raskul, was widely covered in the doctoral dissertation entitled "Didactic foundations of formation of cognitive activity in primary school students", in the dissertation, the cognitive process of primary school students is extensive from the psychological and philosophical side. revealed.

It should be noted that for the development of logical thinking in elementary grades, the use of more logical tasks gives a good result. We turn to elementary school textbooks to work on logical assignments.

Problems and solutions. Thinking is a high form of human mental activity; the process of reflection of objective reality in the mind. Thinking is a tool for knowing the environment, social phenomena, reality, and also the main condition for human activity. It is a higher cognitive process that reflects reality more fully and accurately than intuition, perception, and imagination. It is said to think, to reflect the things and events in reality by thinking, summarizing and mediating the connections between them. Reality is reflected in thinking, perception and imagination relatively deeper and more.

Accelerating and perfecting the thinking process is directly related to increasing logic. Development of logical thinking in primary grades is related to performing logical tasks with them in many ways. the use of different forms and types of logical assignments helps to improve students' thinking. therefore, the

use of logical tasks for the development of worldview and logicity in every student will give good results.

$$\begin{aligned} 123 &= 6 \\ 203 &= 5 \\ 402 &= 6 \\ 233 &=? \end{aligned}$$

when solving this task, students should determine the regularity between the numbers, then the answer to the example will be determined.

$$\begin{aligned} 1+2+3 &= 6 \\ 2+0+3 &= 5 \\ 4+0+2 &= 6 \\ 2+3+3 &= 8 \end{aligned}$$

So'roq o'rnidagi sonni toping !

Examples of this form seem difficult at first glance, but if you look carefully, if the law between the numbers is determined, the answer to the example will be determined quickly. $(8+3)*4=44$

$$(7+9)*2=32$$

$$(7+8)*X=75 \text{ from this equality it is determined that } X=5.$$

The use of logical tasks of this type helps to strengthen the knowledge of students. In the 1st grade mathematics textbook, many topics are aimed at developing students' mathematical thinking skills, finding similarities and differences, and developing thinking through comparison. In particular, Chapter 1 is called "Properties of Things" and contains 10 lessons. All topics are aimed at identifying similarities and differences, identifying differences by comparing things to each other.

In this task, the ideas about dividing the sets into sets according to their properties are described. These and similar assignments serve to expand the thinking of 1st graders.

In this task, the ideas about dividing the sets into sets according to their properties are described. These and similar assignments serve to expand the thinking of 1st graders. The following assignment is given to the student to

complete the assignment.

It is asked which of the objects shown in the picture is shown one at a time.

Here the student's answer should be as follows:

- gate, wall, suri, khontakht, armigchok, cat, teapot, mother, daughter.

Examples of this type have the character of developing logical thinking. Solving examples of this type by students from primary school, using rebuses is aimed at developing logical thinking.

Conclusion. In conclusion, tasks that develop logical thinking are extremely important for primary school students, because young people who think highly in every way are the future of our country. In today's developing age, development of rationality is the need of the hour. that is why it is important to solve tasks that develop logical thinking.

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